

FROM THE MARGINS TO THE SCREEN: GRAMSCI'S ORGANIC INTELLECTUAL IN GHATAK'S *AMAR LENIN***INJAM AHMED MOLLA**

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the interplay between Ritwik Ghatak's 1970 short documentary Amar Lenin (My Lenin) and Antonio Gramsci's theory of organic intellectual. This 20-minute documentary, commissioned by the West Bengal Left Government for Lenin's birth centenary, transcends its political propaganda and becomes a radical pedagogical tool of counter hegemonic education. Through the journey of the unnamed, landless rural protagonist who experiences an ideological awakening via the Jatra (a popular Bengali folk theatre form), the film illustrates Gramsci's notion of organic intellectual who arises organically from within the subaltern classes to articulate the collective struggle. Ghatak's cinematic strategy fuses global Marxist discourse with vernacular aesthetics by reclaiming Lenin as a local figure within subaltern discourse. By using Jatra, the documentary challenges both the bourgeois narratives and metropolitan elitism. Ghatak uses Jatra not only as a narrative device but also as a counter-hegemonic medium that cultivates Gramsci's "good sense" among the oppressed. The paper furthermore investigates how Ghatak himself functions as an organic intellectual who utilizes cinema as a militant pedagogical tool rather than a site of disillusionment. The history of censorship of Amar Lenin including its 1971 ban and renewed suppression in 2025 exposes the State's enduring hegemonic anxieties over radical cultural forms that challenge dominant ideologies.

Keywords : Ritwik Ghatak , Antonio Gramsci , Organic Intellectual, Jatra , Marxism , Counter-Hegemony, Subaltern Consciousness, Revolutionary Cinema , Class Struggle

Introduction :

Antonio Gramsci redefined the role of intellectuals in society in his Prison Notebook (1948) . According to him there are two broad types - traditional intellectual and organic intellectual. Traditional intellectuals are those who believe themselves as autonomous and independent from the ruling hegemonic culture .But according to Gramsci they are not truly independent , knowingly or even unknowingly they are aligned with the hegemonic ruling power. Traditional intellectuals such as priests , teachers , philosophers etc who think they are neutral but often reproduce dominant ideologies through education or institutions. On the

other hand , organic intellectuals are mainly rooted in a particular class , especially in the working class or oppressed groups. They are not just thinkers, they are organizers , leaders who help to develop the class consciousness of their particular groups. They arise from within a particular subaltern class ,articulate its experience , educate and mobilize their groups and thus challenge the dominant hegemony .

Through this Gramscian optic, the protagonist of Ghatak’s 1971 documentary “Amar Lenin” , an unnamed , landless peasant , is a perfect example of organic intellectual. This protagonist’s first encounters with the Leninist thought doesn’t come through any university lecture or party cadre class but through the Jatra , a popular folk theatre of rural Bengal.The protagonist’s journey from a rural village to the urban milieu of Kolkata, where he witness the left wing political atmosphere, and then back to his own village - constitutes not just an geographical loop but also an arc of politicization. When he returned to his village he did not want to attach himself with the ruling class. He did not want to be a metropolitan leader . Rather he used his knowledge by regrounding himself in the practical condition . He refracts Lenin through the prism of village life , instructs , educates , agitates and organizes his fellow villagers to mobilize a practical insurgency against the local dominant landlord class. This pedagogical activity is an important mark of an Organic intellectual. And thus the protagonist becomes a mediator between consciousness and action , between cultural form and political mobilization.

Jatra as counter hegemonic cultural weapon :

In his documentary , Ghatak uses Jatra as a counter hegemonic instrument. Historically , the cultural hierarchies in India were shaped by the colonial aesthetics and the urban modernity and because of these the folk performances which are rooted in rural life ,were often sidelined by the proscenium theatre which was celebrated by the urban elite. In his documentary , Ghatak refuses , rejects , challenges and subverts this hierarchy.He knows that the proscenium stage tends to have a limited reach , primarily catering to an elite urban audience. While the Jatra opens in fields or courtyards , welcoming the elders and the young , workers and caregivers , literate and those who never had a chance to study. This medium is not only entertainment but also it moves , it sings , it explains. And thus Ghatak mobilizes this medium as a political classroom . In the opening sequence of this documentary , the narrator proclaims that *“Lenin ! Lenin came alive ! He is speaking, explaining , roaming around amid this rural night. Suddenly he has leapt out of the pages of books with his message in this bustling port of life”* (Amar Lenin 00:01:41- 00:01:58).This functions as a powerful metaphor which deacademization the marxist thought here and transform the European revolutionary practice into indigenous cultural practice.Historically , Jatra emerged as a religious folk performance of Bengal during the 16th century which mainly celebrates the mythology of Krishna. Jatra’s origin lies in Vaishnavism and Bhakti Movement .The transformation of Jatra during the Swedish Movement(1905-1911) marks its first significant development as a counter hegemonic cultural weapon .Pioneer artist like Mukunda Das deploys Jatra as an anti colonial weapon.He used Jatra’s traditional structure to convey the nationalist messages.The colonial administration’s anxiety about Jatra performance reveals the form’s counter hegemonic potential.For the government it was very difficult to control or censor. Colonial intelligence reports of the time conceded its political potency, noting that this “new genre of jatra” had become “one of the most effective means of spreading seditious feelings,” precisely because it communicated through cultural codes that resonated emotionally while undermining the legitimacy of British rule (qtd. in Pandit 125). The India

People's Theatre Association (IPTA), founded in 1943 as the cultural wing of the Communist Party of India, strategically used traditional folk form to develop the counter hegemonic cultural practice. And this directly influenced Ghatak's later works. In "Amar Lenin" the Jatra performer's presentation of Lenin was not like a distant foreign hero rather Lenin was presented as someone who belongs to the familiar cultural and emotional world of Bengal. The narrator's description - "Lenin is singing the International. It was to be sung. After all, this is a play. The play has made waves in the village (Amar Lenin 00:02:46 -00:02:56)". Here Lenin is singing Bengali and thus the global hero becomes the local figure. Through this documentary's city sequences Ghatak sharply criticized the metropolitan elitism of the left government, where political rallies show us leaders giving speeches that remain distant and abstract, failing to create the kind of emotional connection that the village jatra performance achieved naturally. Rather than being an active participant the protagonist became more of a spectator. The narrator's description - "leader after leaders, so many leaders stands out as one of the incisive moments of social commentary in this documentary. When we closely examine this statement we can see how Ghatak uses the very structure of this language, the repetitive syntax, to explore what had gone wrong in urban leftist politics. This repetitive word "leaders" creates a mechanical rhythm that exactly mirrors what exactly was happening in those urban political organizations - an endless production of authority figures who have become functionally indistinguishable from each other.

Ghatak as an Organic Intellectual

As mentioned early, Gramsci made an important distinction between two types of intellectual. One is Traditional intellectuals who come from privileged backgrounds and often remain disconnected from the working class people. And the other one is the organic intellectual who arise from within a particular subaltern class, articulate its experience, educate and mobilize their groups and thus challenge the dominant hegemony. Ghatak's life story perfectly fits this model. Ghatak himself works as an organic intellectual. He uses cinema to bridge the theory and mass struggle. As Shoma A. Chatterjee records, Ghatak once explained his shift from theatre to film: "We (IPTA) used to give open-air performances where we could rouse and inspire an audience of four or five thousand. But, when I thought of cinema, I thought of the million minds that I could reach at the same time. This is how I came into films, not because I wanted to make films. Tomorrow, if I find a better medium, I'll abandon films..." (Chatterjee 13). Ghatak did not descend from an elite academic or artistic circle and he was never separated from the everyday lives of ordinary working class people. Instead he was born and grew up in a time of great changes and struggle in Bengal during the mid 20th century. Born in Dhaka in 1925, Ghatak had to leave his homeland and migrate to India during the partition of 1947. This painful event deeply affects his life and shapes his view about the world and the art. Ghatak firsthand experienced how East Bengal refugees were ignored and mistreated in post independence India. The pain of being displaced, facing poverty and witnessing the harsh reality of the aftermath of partition became the central theme of both his life and his films. As Shoma A Chatterji notes, "Memories of this heavenly childhood haunted him all his life, wrote film historian Bibekananda Ray. My feet are not on my soil. That is my obstacle. How shall I find another soil and when? Because I have to return to my mother's womb to seek the source of this archetypal idiom, said Ghatak, describing his restive mental state" (10). Most of the cinema of the 1970s, especially known as parallel cinema, carried the tone of deep disillusionment, focusing on the themes of despair, alienation and the fragmented experience of modern life. Against this backdrop, Ghatak's film "Amar Lenin"

stands out in striking contrast. It does not surrender to despair but instead it shows revolutionary possibilities. Where the other films of that time dealt with the political disillusionment and were haunted by the collapse of revolutionary dreams, “Amar Lenin” offers something radically different. For Ghatak history was not a graveyard of failed movements rather it is a field of unfinished tasks where new ideas always emerge. And it becomes most visible in the ending of “Amar Lenin” where men, women, elder, children along with their cattle uniting together to claim their land. This scene is not accidental rather it is a deliberate act for showing that revolution is not about destruction but about unity, care and it is a collective process. The inclusion of animals alongside the human may seem unusual but it powerfully symbolizes a vision of life where the whole community including human and animal is the part of the struggle for survival. For Ghatak Leninism was not something outside or accidental but a natural result of people’s long fight for equality. Ghatak mobilizes Lenin as a local figure rather than an outsider, global leader. In the final sequence of “Amar Lenin” is one of the most striking moments where the narrator proclaims that “Land. The land that they have ploughed but they never possessed. Today they will plough the land and make it their own. They stand on guard. They plough. The soil. The golden soil. On their ploughs the flags flutter. In their midst stands Lenin. They claim he is their Lenin. “My Lenin”, they roar. Comrade Lenin. The plough, the soil, the flag and Comrade Lenin. Comrade Lenin. They burst with happiness. Their bodies sway to the rhythm of dance. Their joy knows no bounds. They measure the harvest and distribute it. At the same time they keep vigil. Always standing beside them is Comrade Lenin. Long live freedom! Long live freedom! On the roads, on the river banks, in the fields of the village, they march with their torches (moshal). It is the spontaneous expression of their joy! They are victorious. They will be victorious because Lenin stands with them and guards them. They know that their struggle is Lenin’s struggle. The two have mixed and melded into one. They are not alone. They have never been alone. From every corner of the earth, they shout, “My Lenin!” (Amar Lenin 00.16.20 -00.19.57). As the narration continues, Lenin is portrayed not as a distant historical figure but as a living presence: “In their midst stands Lenin. They claim he is their Lenin. “My Lenin”, they roar.” And thus Ghatak becomes a perfect example of an organic intellectual who can translate abstract theory into the lived experience of ordinary people so that ideology becomes inseparable from practice. The villagers’ joy is not naive but it is political. It expressed a deep consciousness that their victory is a part of a larger global struggle. By presenting Lenin as both symbol and companion Ghatak creates a new grammar of revolutionary cinema.

Censorship and Hegemonic Suppression

Gramsci’s concept of hegemony is especially useful to understand the reason behind the banning of this documentary, “Amar Lenin”, in such different moments - first in the year 1971 under Indira Gandhi’s Congress Government and later in the year of 2025 under TMC Government in West Bengal. According to Gramsci the ruling class maintains power and dominance not only through coercion but by controlling culture, knowledge and any opposite ideology. Those these parties often project themselves as secular and progressive, their actions reveal similar anxieties towards a revolutionary imagery. In the year 1971, censor board ordered to cut the scenes where peasants plough the land under Lenin’s Portrait. By erasing Lenin’s symbolic presence during the collective act of land reclaiming, the state wanted to prevent what Gramsci terms as “counter hegemonic” consciousness. Indira Gandhi’s later decision to lift the ban and awarded Ghatak with Padma Shri reflects another strategy of

hegemony. The same pattern visible in the year 2025 where the West Bengal Government ordered to block the centenary screenings of this documentary at local school. "Amar Lenin" was banned not because of its form but because it shows a path to the peasants and the workers that their collective struggle can over turn the authority that oppresses them for years. And thus the banning history of this documentary clearly shows us that the dominant power always tries to neutralize the counter hegemony.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Ritwik Ghatak's "Amar Lenin" offers more than a documentary on a revolutionary leader, it is a cinematic masterpiece which explores the concepts of Antonio Gramsci's concept of Organic Intellectual. Ghatak's protagonist is an unnamed landless peasant whose consciousness rises via Jatra. Like an organic intellectual, the protagonist arises from within a particular subaltern class, articulates his experience, educates and mobilizes his groups and thus challenges the dominant hegemony. By subverting the traditional form Ghatak here uses Jatra as a counter hegemonic instrument which challenges both the bourgeois narratives and metropolitan elitism. At the same time, the documentary exposes how the state or the dominant power always tries to suppress the revolutionary thought. "Amar Lenin" is not only a tribute to Lenin but also a case study how culture itself can become a ground for building class awareness. Ghatak himself becomes an organic intellectual who uses cinema to bridge theory and mass struggle. In doing so he just shows us that cinema is not only just for entertainment but can act as a force for social transformation. Even after the four decades, the documentary reminds us that genuine social change can not be achieved only through political movements or organizations, it also requires a cultural struggle. And in this struggle, the intellectuals, artists, filmmakers have a responsibility to stand with the peasant and workers, not as an outsider but as a companion, but as a comrade in the creation of a new history.

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